

INTRODUCTION

Art was central to [Rights for Time](#), a global network of academics and practitioners aiming to shift the discourse and practice of humanitarian protection by exploring how time conditions war, displacement, and violence. The network's commissioned projects were diverse in this regard, their outputs ranging from traditional textual and visual media -- including books, pamphlets, collections of literary stories, photographs, videos, and animations -- to sculptured material, performances, soundscapes, and dynamic installations. These wonderful and challenging outputs are shared online through a dedicated website, where the projects are contextualized in their respective countries: Kenya, Uganda, Cameroon, Rwanda, Palestine, Iraq, and Pakistan. To complement the website, this report elaborates on the variety of art outputs deployed in the network's projects. Based on reviews of projects and interviews with their leads and art practitioners, it reveals the themes which make art uniquely capable of understanding trauma and alleviating suffering in the context of humanitarian protection. *Art Represents* a unique and extraordinary capacity to reflect individual and collective experiences. In this regard, *Art Convenes* not only artists and practitioners, but also community members and the wider public, including policymakers and local leaders. *Art Researches* in ways that further standard research practices, as well as innovates on how knowledge may be produced in places where formal research is difficult. In addition to qualitatively enriching research, *Art Heals* affected communities, art practitioners themselves, and the broader public sphere. Given these capacities, art evolves over time, its myriad forms capable of meeting the present moment. By being able to fund and support art outputs, the Rights for Time Network has shown the effectiveness of art and artmaking in challenging, transforming, and widening our conception of time.

COMMISSIONED PROJECTS

1. [African Initiative for Mankind Progress Organisation \(Rwanda\)](#)

When They Sung at Me, I Sang Back

2. [Azadi Kenya \(Kenya\)](#)

Ethical Storytelling and Photography Fellowship

3. [Facilitation for Peace and Development \(Uganda\)](#)

Film-in-Participatory Action Learning for the Integration of Children Born of War

4. [Hussaini Foundation \(Pakistan\)](#)

Youth Time Against Trauma

5. Iraqi Development Association for Human Development Organization (Iraq)

Etched in Memory: Untold Stories of Mandaean's Past and Present Life in Iraq

6. [Njabala Foundation \(Uganda\)](#)

Pillars of Rectitude

7. [Palestine Trauma Centre \(Palestine\)](#)

Learning from Gaza: Mental Health Paradigms from the Grassroots

8. [Palestine Writing Workshop \(Palestine\)](#)

Burning Time

9. [Tamer Institute for Community Education \(Palestine\)](#)

Where Did Home Go?

10. [The Forest Creative Loft \(Cameroon\)](#)

Going Back through Memory Lane

ART REPRESENTS

Art enables the representation of all that cannot be discursively articulated. In some cases, art provides the sole means of representing trauma, as it enables the expression of a traumatic past beyond the strictures and self-censorship of other outlets, such as formal interviews. In Cameroon, for instance, expression through art broke what the community refers to as a ‘silent war,’ in which affected individuals are conditioned to maintain the status quo. In similarly challenging an oppressive status quo in Uganda, where female artists in the past and present are sidelined, “Pillars of Rectitude” enabled participating artists to research their own artistic inheritance, share it through a wide-reaching symposium, and represent the process through sculptural techniques; the formalization of a social history in an abstract work of art opened up means for the participants to not only represent their story, but also to consider what it means to withhold, negate, and safeguard in their own terms.

In Palestine, what children under house arrest experience is hard to speak about. The colonial forces themselves, but also the internalization of fear by their families, inflict on children a silence towards expressing both their experience and their basic human response of anger and frustration. Because silence is weaponized, “Where Did Home Go?” offered children the chance to be expressive through the safety and anonymity of art. “When direct expression is absent, art becomes a mediator of expression,” as the project lead explained, and the project’s strategy

was not to rely on predetermined forms of expression. The final collection of stories was premised on navigating the space in which silence can exist and vocality can be chosen in a way that is dictated by the participants themselves.

Another art form, that of human voice, was central to the project in

Rwanda. “When They Sung at Me, I Sang Back” brought the human voice in all its effusiveness to bear upon a divided society. Sharing through song the experience of loss, of

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grief, and of connection allowed participants to embody their narrative and represent their plight humanely and without the stigmas of victimhood. “An artist who sings to the people has the voice, the agency, of their own experience.” (When They Sung at Me) The audience was able to hear the melody, see the singers, and connect with their passion. In Kenya, too, the creation and representation of art brought about the human dimension: “those who experienced trauma are dignified in the process as artmakers rather than as victims.” Considering the expressive agency of art is not at the expense of confronting the difficult past; it allows, to borrow from “Pillar of Rectitude,” to consider the weight of the past alongside nourishment in the present.

ART CONVENES

The practice of art lends itself naturally, though not exclusively, to convening the public. Such convening varied from rural amphitheaters to urban exhibition spaces. Showcasing artwork brought together not only artists and community members related to the project, but also the wider public, which included academics, members of government, NGOs, sportspeople, and leaders from civil society. In some instances, as in Cameroon, the ecological space reflected the ethos of the project: the exhibition was held in the middle of a forest, disrupting socioeconomic hierarchies, as it brought urban elites into the countryside. So, too, in Rwanda, the exhibition allowed not only the affected community but also diverse parts of civil society to learn more about the Rwandan genocide and to become aware of its effects into the present. Even mundane questions, which reveal the subtle impact of conflict over time, have the chance to be represented; the exhibition of photographs by “When They Sung at Me, I Sang Back” showcased everyday issues facing the community, including access to water and sanitation.

Art provides a safe space not only for well-meaning members of the public, but also officials who are tasked with humanitarian protection but who usually undertake their tasks from a comfortable and unexamined distance. In this light, convening around art disarmed the agendas of external participants. Through the exhibition space, Cameroon was able to meet with politicians and probe them about the importance of a local intervention in ways that would have been difficult to orchestrate bureaucratically, or outright impossible.

Similarly, in Uganda, “Pillar of Rectitude” was able to reach a large public audience which would not have otherwise considered an issue as seeming particular as the preservation, celebration, and support of female artists in the country. In all cases, the exhibition room or the symposium space, the gallery and the informal meeting room, provided safety and trust for attendees to learn beyond, while also negotiating, the prejudice of the status quo.

ART RESEARCHES

Human experience cannot be reduced to a set of research practices. As members of Uganda's "Pillars of Rectitude" put it: "What sets art apart is how it relates, first and foremost, to the capacious personal story; art is wide; it opens up possibilities of form and expression that cannot be boxed." "Pillar of Rectitude" conceived of participants as researchers by virtue of their artistic practice; tasked with studying female artists from the 1960s in Uganda, each participant engaged in archival, memorial, and artistic quests to better understand their historical context. In doing so, the participants built on the agency they have cultivated as artists but also understood their practice as furthering research related to memory and conservation, building conceptual connections between the present and the past. In "Where Did Home Go?", a project in Palestine, the power of art came to the fore: interviews were insufficient for understanding everyday oppression in Palestine, specifically the control of bodies in the city of Jerusalem. Through art, in contrast, the human experience was freed from constraint and participants were able to present themselves, imagine their stories, and open up possibilities for empathy to the audience.

Research is often mired in standardized forms of proficiency, the capacity for participants to speak the language of the researcher. For vulnerable communities, especially children, and for participants from rural areas who did not complete a standardized education, discursive and jargon-based articulation may be insufficient or alienating. In Pakistan, art was the way out, allowing for engagement with concepts and experiences without the weight of a specified articulation. In "Youth Time Against Trauma," the act of creation, because it was facilitated emphatically, democratized access to expression. As the project lead explained, "The children were surprised by their own capacity to create an artwork and then to take ownership of their work."

Aiding research, art also allows hitherto unknown tensions to emerge into the threshold of recognition. Such was the case in Cameroon, where "Going Back Through Memory Lane" showed how "hidden conflicts around citizens can often be revealed in their art practices." When it comes to difficult or taboo topics, where formal research practice is difficult or impossible, art allowed for creative and malleable forms which navigated social and political constraints while maintaining seriousness and rigor. In Iraq, accessing the minority Mandaean community and representing its plight was possible through artistic practices which are not as susceptible to censorship as official interviews or focus group discussions. "Etched in Memory" found that the Mandaean community has its own inherited codes of conduct related to privacy and ritual, and art provided the project with a means of reaching them respectfully and on their own terms. In fact, towards the end of the project, community leaders began deploying the resources of the network to co-author the first ever

bilingual brochure about the group. Such an output -- at once artistic and research-oriented -- would not have been possible otherwise.

Art also opens up ethical questions hitherto unexplored in specific projects. In “Where Did Home Go?” the facilitator had to consider the complex dynamic of leading arts workshops in a part of Palestine other than her own. Reflections on the subjectivity of the project organizers became central the moment they began mediating an artistic form; whereas formal research has its own ethical guidelines and requirements, which in itself has an important role but could easily devolve into the application of unreflective principles, the expansiveness of art pushed the project leads to reflect thoroughly on their own positionality. This provided not only an opportunity for personal growth and site-specific understanding, but also enhanced all other elements of the project, including research, because it revealed to all those involved the complex dynamics that are difficult to distill in a generalized ethical guideline.

ART HEALS

Part and parcel of what it excavates intellectually, art has the capacity to heal the participating communities, especially when they have undergone compound harm. In Uganda, the screening of a film about children born of war opened up space for dialogue and constructive confrontation; in the first screening, there were hundreds of men, women, and children, including a few of the perpetrating soldiers themselves. After the film screening, a man stood up and begged for forgiveness: “I was a soldier.” And one of the children responded: “We forgive you.” This dynamic encounter, facilitated by the safety of an art space, is contrasted to the idea of a tribunal which, while having its own role to play in reckoning with the past and attaining justice, would not have been feasible in this community. Film -- and its profound healing effects -- is also a more cost-effective way of scaling such dialogue, as the experience is sedimented in a transportable form without the movement of participants; art, in this sense, distills an experience that can be printed, duplicated, and taken across the globe. As such, the act of healing through art can outlive the project itself.

Healing is also a collective process. In “Burning Time,” a philosophy of art allowed the project to place individual stories in Palestine as part of the public sphere, rendering the boundary porous between the self and society. As the project lead explained, of the project’s outlook on the occupation: “You are not alone; you are an individual story in a greater social story.” Depersonalizing the trauma in Palestine was a therapeutic process, and the final output, a book of creative writing, symbolized this philosophy, sublimating the everyday experience into an output that is capable of moving society at large. Art, in this case, removed the idea of absolute victimhood because the artist was able to situate themselves in a larger social world that is dynamic and includes both suffering and joy, victimhood and healing. Similarly, at the Palestine Trauma Center, practitioners emerged in the midst of the genocide, to facilitate workshops for the children, sometimes in the middle of the rubble; in those brief moments of respite, they laughed for the first time.

Over the course of eleven workshops in Pakistan, “Youth Time Against Trauma” was able to evolve the forms of art available for healing. New themes emerged from this organic approach; the trope of the super hero, for example, allowed youth to bypass the most explicit aspects of their trauma while building resilience. In this light, the project innovated on artistic metaphors and available media, ultimately organizing sessions around origami, meditation, massage, the creation of massage oils, gardening, and stitching. The tactile,

bodily, and creative outlets allowed for the creation of art -- a physical piece of work -- while facilitating conversations about inner strength and future resilience.

In Kenya, “The Azadi Project” innovated on the forms of art available to participants, letting them take the lead. In one workshop, a member developed not only a drawing but also how it would be framed, taking pieces of glass and bottle tops to represent her drawing. The capacity to frame, literally and figuratively, one’s own experience necessitates an open and organic approach to the usage of art. The curator, in this instance, served only as a guide, allowing each artist to develop their own instinctive mode of expression. In many cases, this led to the usage of culturally specific forms, such as African print, which would not have been the purview of a predetermined artistic program.

ART FUNDING

The powerful and varying artworks produced by the projects is a testament to what a network grant can achieve, even if over a relatively short amount of time. Yet, given the network's focus on time and temporality, the projects revealed the importance of funding projects for longer stretches of time in order to allow host organizations to dwell on the critical relationship to art, navigate their context, and build relationships of trust with their community. This is particularly the case for communities in the Global South where public funding for the arts is absent or inconsistent.

Funding the arts is even more essential for organizations working through humanitarian crises in the present. While the network provides a strong evidence base for supporting arts outputs, the projects highlighted the importance of thinking about long-term organizational support. The NGO sector in Palestine does not usually have the privilege of using art, with the occupation in particular obstructing how resources may be used; as a result, many practitioners are not able to focus on art without substantial support for their basic work.

Creativity needs time and has its own conditions and contexts. In Rwanda, the project opened up possibilities for future work around photography and recording as a means of preserving culture for the next generation. There is a fear of losing diverse culture due to the country's assimilation policies and art is a safe and politically uncontentious mode of preservation. The network grant has pushed the project to incorporate methods of preservation in the future, and to explore funding strategies for the arts that allow for greater continuity.

